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An EU Interministerial Action for supporting consumers to compare the prices of alternative fuels

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the road transport is considered as a polluting action for the environment, which consumes over 80% of the total final energy used in the transport sector and contributes over 75% to its total CO₂ emissions. EU has set ambitious target to reduce Greenhouse Gas emissions to 80–95% below 1990-levels by 2050 and thus policies promote the propagation of eco-friendly vehicles at the market, i.e. Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Directive 2014/94/EU. This Directive establishes a common framework of measures for the deployment of EU alternative fuels infrastructure in order to minimise dependence on oil and to mitigate the environmental impact of transport by setting out the minimum requirements for the building-up of alternative fuels infrastructure, including recharging points for electric vehicles, refuelling points for natural gas (LNG and CNG) and hydrogen. As decarbonising transport is a major priority of EU, the display of fuels information shall not confuse the consumer. To increase consumer awareness and provide fuel price transparency in a consistent way across the Union, the Commission empowered to adopt, by means of implementing acts, a common methodology for alternative fuels unit price comparison in accordance to the Article 7, para. 3 of Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Directive 2014/94/EU, based on the method of "euros/national currencies per 100 km" will be applied, as established in the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/732 of 17 May 2018.

This study presents a transparent and understandable methodology identified and evaluated by NTUA in order to allow the fuel price comparison under one common fuel unit by avoiding assumptions, exclusions and vehicle segmentation. Key factor for this methodology is the application of engine power (kW) for all calculations, as a common and understandable parameter for all vehicles in respect with consumption data resulted by the uniform WLTP database. The application of the NTUA methodology for a common fuel price in the cases of Greece, Germany, The Netherlands resulted in the objective comparison for the variety of fuels available. Moreover, Electric Vehicles presented lower €/100 km prices in a range of 10-80%, compared to the other examined vehicles for Greece and The Netherlands.

INTRODUCTION

Road transport plays an important role in today's EU economy and society with a large impact on growth and employment, whereas effective transport systems are fundamental for the European companies' ability to compete in the world economy (Rackowski et al. 2017). More precisely, the automotive industry participated on 4% of the European GDP and provides 12 million jobs, or otherwise 5.6% of the employed population in Europe (ACEA 2014). On the other hand, it contributes about one-fifth of the European Union's (EU) total emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂), the main Greenhouse Gas (GHG), 75% of which originates from passenger cars (EEA 2015, EU 2015). It is noted that transport is the only sector in the EU, where GHG emissions are still rising (DG-CLIMA 2016).

However, Europe has decided to lead the way in the global transition to a decarbonized and sustainable society by meeting Paris Agreement commitments. Since 2009, EU has set mandatory targets for the average CO₂ emissions of each vehicle manufacturer at 130 CO₂/km and 95 CO₂/km for 2015 and 2021, respectively (European Commission, 2009). The European Commission's 2011 White Paper for transport, it is significantly noted the importance of minimizing CO₂ emissions in order to make the transition to a low carbon economy. In its 2014 climate-energy package communication, the

EC has put more ambitious goals for 2030: 40% GHG reduction compared to 1990 and 27% share of renewables of EU energy consumption (EC 2011a,b; EESC, 2014). Furthermore, the EC has recently proposed a 27% improvement in energy efficiency (Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council, 2014). The EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED) sets binding targets of 20% (16.7% in 2015 as reported by Eurostat 2017) for gross final energy consumption and 10% (6.7% in 2015 referred by Eurostat 2017) for transport fuels to come from renewable energy sources by 2020. However, the new regulatory framework includes an energy efficiency target for the EU for 2030 of 32.5% with an upwards revision clause by 2023, together with the recently agreed 32% renewable energy target for the EU for 2030 (EC, 2018). Furthermore, the transportation sector has been set a target of reducing GHG emission by 60% by 2050 relative to 1990 levels, based on the European Commission's 2011 Transport White Paper targets.

To address these issues, environmental policies are mainly aimed at switching the type of fuel used in conventional vehicles in order to reduce emissions and thus lead to a low-carbon society, spurring the use of Alternative Fuel Vehicles (AFVs). The generic term AFV refers to vehicles that utilize electricity, hydrogen, compressed natural gas, liquified petroleum gas, ethanol, biodiesel and other non-diesel and petrol fuels. However, these vehicles are representing a small percentage of the automotive market ($\approx 2.7\%$). Consequently, the steep annual reduction of CO₂ emissions in this case, might be a result of changes in the share of each fuel type within AFV each year (Pastorello and Mellios, 2015). The increased participation of AFVs could replace a significant portion of the EU fleet's petroleum/gasoline consumption and mitigate emissions and security issues related to oil extraction, combustion, political conditions, etc. (Hackbarth and Madlener 2013; Nanaki et al. 2016).

However, the behavior of consumers towards the purchase of AFVs is ambiguous. Studies have indicated the advantages perceived by consumers as well as the reasons for which consumers are negative in order to buy AFV (Egbue and Long 2012; Hafez and Bhattacharya 2017, Hidrue et al. 2011; Krause et al. 2013; Krupa et al. 2014; Larson 2014; Morton et al. 2015). Most of them appealed that the major obstacle is related to the cost, which are higher than those of conventional fuel vehicles. Although electricity costs are much lower than petroleum fuel costs, this difference is not sufficient to compensate for the higher upfront costs required for the purchase of AFVs compared to conventional fuel vehicles. However, new technological developments are expected to be implemented in the near future that will reduce costs and improve AFVs efficiency. In any case, price of AFVs may influence consumers' willingness to adopt AFVs (Junquera et al. 2016). Further studies are focused on the consumer preferences for AFVs (Hoen and Koetse, 2014, Qian and Soopramanien, 2011; Tran et al., 2013). A few studies are focused on the consumer preferences by comparing all available types of AFVs as well as the status of competition within the market of vehicles, whereas other studies have analyzed the effects of vehicle-related policies, legislative framework and market acceptance (Achtmeit et al. 2012; Eggers and Eggers, 2011; Hong et al., 2012; Wolinetz and Axsen, 2017).

In terms of alternative fuels, positive and negative characteristics of the fuel may offset each other to a substantial degree, leaving market share to be determined by price and intangible or unpredictable factors such as consumer perceptions of fuel "quality," or individual willingness to pay for fuels with social rather than private benefits. An important factor for the promotion and successful market integration of alternative fuels is related to the comprehensive and transparent consumer information. The perceived fuel prices significantly influence consumers in their decision when buying a vehicle and therefore a new approach in respect with fuel pricing is recommended. For this reason, the price-performance ratio of different fuels must be made comparable, thus offering a more informed decision to the consumers. Moreover, the attractiveness of alternative fuels must be made more visible and thus strengthened in the competitive fuel market.

In price information law, no provision has been made for comparison of the different fuel options. Acceptance of a pricing variant is currently based essentially on the expectations of the sector of the public being addressed directly by the respective price – that is, those consumers who already use a corresponding vehicle. The fact that consumers take notice not only of the price of their "own" fuel but all fuel prices, and will later include this information in their vehicle purchase decisions, is something that currently plays no role in the legal definition of the relevant sector of the public. For this reason, the pricing has to be adapted to the changing fuel market.

The EU institutions have recognized this, and the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Directive adopted in October 2014 (EE 2014) now specifies in recital 51: "Simple and easy-to-compare information on the prices of different fuels could play an important role in enabling vehicle users to better evaluate the relative cost of individual fuels available on the market.

Therefore, when fuel prices are displayed at a fuel station, in particular for natural gas and hydrogen, it should be possible for unit price comparison to conventional fuels, such as '1 petrol litre equivalent', to be displayed for information purposes." To this regard, Art. 7 paragraph 3 of the Directive states: "Where appropriate, and in particular for natural gas and hydrogen, when fuel prices are displayed at a fuel station, a comparison between the relevant unit prices shall be displayed for information purposes. The display of this information shall not mislead or confuse the user. To increase consumer awareness and provide for fuel price transparency in a consistent way across the Union, the Commission shall be empowered to adopt, by means of implementing acts, a common methodology for alternative fuels unit price comparison."

This Directive establishes a common framework of measures for the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure in the Union in order to minimise dependence on oil and to mitigate the environmental impact of transport. It sets out minimum requirements for the building-up of alternative fuels infrastructure, including recharging points for electric vehicles and refuelling points for natural gas (LNG and CNG) and hydrogen, to be implemented by means of Member States' national policy frameworks, as well as common technical specifications for such recharging and refuelling points, and user information requirements.

Though alternative fuels are not an innovation in themselves, the new price comparison system will have to be disseminated as a new idea. The categories of adopters range from innovators to early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards (Rogers, 2003). These different consumer types have different needs and thus require a range of channels for communication.

The purpose of the current study is to increase consumer awareness and provide fuel price transparency in a consistent way by presenting an implementable conversion methodology focusing on the unit price comparison of all available fuels under the common unit of "euros/national currencies per 100 km", in accordance to the Article 7, para. 3 of 2014/94/EU of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/732 of 17 May 2018. In this study, the analysis is focused on three Member States of EU, i.e. Greece, Germany and The Netherlands by using all available fuel and vehicle market data, as resulted by the uniform WLTP database.

METHODS AND DATA

NTUA Methodology in respect with a common fuel price

The methodology developed by NTUA is performed in four (4) steps by taking into account all passenger cars available in EU market ranked under the new Worldwide harmonized Light-duty Test Procedure (WLTP). WLTP is a global, harmonized standard for determining the levels of pollutants, CO₂ emissions and fuel consumption of traditional and hybrid cars, as well as the range of fully electric vehicles. The WLTP Regulation is adopted by the Commission on June 1st, 2017 and it will be mandatory for all new car registrations from September 1st, 2018 (EC, 2017). It is implemented in EU in order to review the type-approval procedure for passenger cars due to the increasing divergence between real-world and type-approval fuel consumption, as well as the difficulty to evaluate the actual effect of the CO₂ reduction technologies (Marotta and Tutuianu, 2012).

Key parameter of the NTUA proposed methodology is the engine power (kW) of each vehicle. The selection of engine power as key parameter for the calculations driving to the fuel common unit is based on the fact that it is representative to each vehicle and completely understandable to all consumers, whereas is a sense of fair play by avoiding assumptions. It is noted that for this study, sales of second-hand vehicles are excluded.

The first step of the proposed methodology is related to EU level and all representative common vehicle units (vehicle segment categories from A to J) are gathered by emphasizing on engine power, whereas the unified WLTP database is used for collecting data regarding the vehicle consumption of passenger vehicle available in EU market. In this step, the mean WLTP consumption per kW of engine per fuel type is calculated. The second step is performed in Member States level. In this stage, the fuel mean prices of the last quarter are calculated and the vehicle ranked in the first position of sales is selected, whereas the engine power of this vehicle is applied as the basis for further calculations. In the third step, the equivalent consumption per 100 km per fuel type is extrapolated for the vehicle and specific engine power selected. In the final step, the price is integrated taking into consideration the equivalent consumption for each fuel type (**Figure 1**).

In particular, a vehicle database is suggested to be developed including vehicles registered in EU level for the last year (and will be updated every six months). This database will consist of vehicle models and manufactures of vehicles as well as fuel type, fuel consumption and engine power. This information will be utilized for the next step in which calculations of normalized vehicle consumption and fuel price will be performed. As it shown in **Figure 2**, all different segments of vehicles as well as all available fuel types in EU will be taken into account to the database and the final results.

Figure 1. Steps related to the common fuel price methodology.

Figure 2. Proposed approach following the fuel price calculation in respect with the common unit of "euros/national currencies per 100 km".

Model analysis and simulation in three MS

As already noted the implementation and evaluation of the proposed methodology is performed in three MS of the European Union, i.e. Greece, Germany and The Netherlands. First of all, the initialization of the methodology parameters will be performed. Following, the parameters are presented generally in respect with the implementation of the common fuel price methodology. **Figure 3** shows these parameters including the mean price of each fuel type to be presented at filling station (A) and the combined fuel consumption per vehicle derived from the database(B). As it shown, vehicle fuel consumption (B) measured in WLTP will be normalized to the power engine of each vehicle(C).

A (€/sell unit): Mean Price per fuel type per selling unit (lt, kWh, kg), MS level, mean value of last quarter

B (sell unit/100 km): Database with WLTP values (only), for vehicles registered within Europe.

Fuel type (a, b, c, d, e, f)	C = Equivalent unit (per kW/100 km)
Diesel, Petrol, LPG	lt
Electricity	kWh
CNG, Hydrogen (Fuel cell)	kg

Figure 3. Introduction to methodology parameters.

Moreover, the representative vehicle will be defined in relation to market trends. The bestselling vehicle will be selected and fuel prices will be calculated for its specific power engine (P). It is suggested updating the information about the representative engine power every three months (see also **Figure 1**). **Figure 4** presents the formula by which the fuel prices will be calculated by utilizing the information gathered from the previous steps. Initially, the mean WLTP consumption per fuel type of each vehicle type is divided by its kW of engine. Afterwards, the resulted values are multiplied by the engine power (P) of the bestselling vehicle during the last three (3) months. Finally, the resulted values are multiplied by the mean fuel prices (€/sale unit) based on the last three months in order to calculate the common fuel unit. These calculations are performed every three (3) months for renewing the results in respect with EU fuel market.

Figure 4. Calculation of equivalent consumption resulted in the common fuel unit of "euros/national currencies per 100 km".

Table 1 presents all the relevant vehicle data resulted by Greece, Germany and The Netherlands for the 2nd quarter of 2019 (i.e. mean values), which is necessary in order to proceed with the application of the proposed methodology. For the calculations and data extrapolation, the numerical computing environment of MATLAB software is used.

Table 1. Initialization of parameters for three MS

EU MS	Number of vehicles	Range of Engine Power (kW)	Average Engine Power (Kw)	Consumption Data	Period (Years)
Greece (*)	1237	13 to 467	76	WLTP combined	2017-2018
Germany (**)	808	48 to 390	112		
Netherlands (***)	1263	13 to 1100	87		

(*) http://www.fuelprices.gr/deltia_d.view and <https://gr.fuelo.net/fuel/type/methane/3months?lang=en>

(**) <https://www.mwv.de/statistiken/verbraucherpreise/> and <https://de.fuelo.net/fuel/type/lpg/2years?lang=en>

(***) <https://waterstof-tanken.nu/waterstof-tanken> and <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/81567NED/table?fromstatweb>

Additionally it is noted that same fuels are not financially comparable between the the three examined MS, as the fuel cost is corresponded to variable taxation regime. **Table 2** presents the current price in € per fuel unit in respect with Greece, Germany and The Netherlands. In case of Greece due to the limited network of electric vehicle (EV) charging stations as well as the great variance of electricity tariffs, the price of residential electricity is used for calculations.

Table 2. Current prices in €/fuel unit

Fuel	Greece (€/fuel unit)	Germany (€/fuel unit)	The Netherlands (€/fuel unit)
Diesel	1.41	1.31	1.38
Petrol	1.65	1.53	1.70
CNG	0.88	1.05	1.02
Electricity	0.19	0.30	0.16
LPG	0.82	0.62	0.66
Hydrogen	-	9.95	9.95

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 illustrates the data resulted by the application of the proposed methodology for Greece, Germany and The Netherlands, as expressed in €/100 km. The analysis included all available vehicles types in each MS, i.e. diesel, petrol, CNG, electric, LPG, hydrogen, hydride as well as plug-in hybrid electric vehicle (PHEV). By evaluating the resulted data, it is indicated that lower fuel price expressed in €/100 km is related to Electric Vehicles in case of Greece and Netherlands as well as PHEV in case of Germany. However, more expensive fuels could lead to comparable running costs (e.g. hydrogen vehicles in comparison to petrol vehicles), as resulted by the example of Germany.

In Greece, the €/100 km value resulted by electricity is reduced by 67%, 78%, 55%, 78%, 67% and 10%, compared to vehicles fueled by diesel, petrol, CNG, LPG, hydrogen as well as hydride and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, respectively. For Netherlands, the €/100 km value resulted by electricity is reduced by 71%, 80%, 69%, 65%, 68% and 67% in comparison to diesel, petrol, CNG, LPG, hydrogen as well as hydride and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, respectively. For Germany and by emphasizing on electricity, it is shown that the €/100 km value is decreased by 31%, 51%, 32%, 52%, 51% and 18%, compared to diesel, petrol, CNG, LPG, hydrogen as well as hydride, respectively. It is noted that the differences in fuels between the three MS are related to the different taxation regime.

Figure 5. Indicative €/100 km price results for variable fuel type vehicles.

It is obvious that the proposed methodology presented all fuel types in a comparable way in order to support consumers to easily compare between fuel costs. Although the proposed framework generates useful results, it is also acknowledged that there are certain limitations. These limitations are related to fuel efficiency data, which should be as detailed as possible in order to conduct data analysis and assessment in a comprehensive manner.

CONCLUSION

Based on IEA (2016), 23% of all global emissions were generated by transport sector. Thus, regarding the GHG emissions, the transport sector is among the main contributors to CO₂ equivalents in the EU-28 to the energy and conversion sector. That's why EU has decided to minimize the environmental impact of the transport sector by promoting actions which will reduce the GHG emissions by 54-67% in 2050, compared with 1990. The measures taken include greater fuel efficiency, less carbon intensive energy carriers and better utilization of transport networks (European Commission, 2011a) by spurring the use of Alternative fuel vehicles (AFVs) that use gaseous fuel, electricity, hydrogen or a liquid other than gasoline or diesel. It is anticipated that the propagation of eco-friendly AFVs will have a positive effect on both the EU environment and economy. However, all types of fuels are expressed in variable sale units, whereas the energy content per sales also varies greatly among different fuel options in some cases. For this reason an important factor for the successful market introduction of the eco-friendly alternative fuel vehicles is the comprehensive and transparent consumer information.

This study is one of the first attempts to provide a quantitative and systematic methodology allowing consumers to compare between the fuel costs of vehicles and different fuels in a common fuel unit, i.e. €/100 km, following the Article 7, para. 3 of 2014/94/EU. In this study, an analysis framework is presented that integrates a bottom-up dynamic accounting methodology by combining fuel type per selling unit (L, kWh, kg, etc.), mean WLTP consumption per fuel type and engine power (kW).

The current analysis performed by focusing on WLTP data from Greece, Germany and The Netherlands revealed that €/100 km unit resulted in the objective comparison for the variety of fuels available in their markets. It is indicated that the prices of €/100 km related to Electric Vehicles are lower in a range of 10-80%, compared to the other fueled-vehicles in

case of Greece and Netherlands, whereas competitive price is also achieved in case of Electric Vehicles in Germany. The proposed methodology provides a transparent and understandable approach, which can be easily adapted by the Member States of EU, taking into consideration the fact that the fuel market fair play is a key factor for the EU continued economic growth and avoiding local fuel market pressure. The advantages of this methodology can be summarized on the fact that there are no assumptions, no exclusions and no vehicle segmentation. It is based on engine power, which is a common and understandable parameter that can be examined among all vehicles and thus under this approach all vehicles available in the EU market can be considered properly.

However, this study indicated that further research has to be conducted in terms of fuel benefits of AV technology under real conditions through model simulations as well as under variable AV technology penetration levels. It is noted that the need exists to investigate the fuel efficiency benefits of AFV under real-world situations; taking into account that model differentiates fuel benefits on time of day, day of week, road type and vehicle type.

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REFERENCES

- Achtnicht, M., Buhler, G., and C. Hermeling. 2012. The impact of fuel availability on demand for alternative-fuel vehicles. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 17 (3): 262-269.
- ACEA. 2014. Reducing CO₂ emissions from cars and vans - background. European Automobile Manufacturers' Association.
- European Commission. 2011a. A roadmap for moving to a competitive low carbon economy in 2050, Communication from the commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Brussels.
- European Commission. 2011b. White paper roadmap to a single European transport area towards a competitive and resource efficient transport system /*COM/2011/0144 final */.
- European Commission. 2017. Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1151
- European Commission. 2018, https://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_STATEMENT-18-3997_en.htm
- EEA. 2015. Final energy consumption by sector and fuel — European Environment Agency. <http://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/final-energy-consumption-by-sector-9/assessment>
- Egbue O., and S. Long. 2012. Barriers to widespread adoption of electric vehicles: an analysis of consumer attitudes and perceptions, *Energy Policy* 48: 717-729.
- Eggers F., and F. Eggers. 2011. Where have all the flowers gone? Forecasting green trends in the automotive industry with a choice-based conjoint adoption model. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 78 (1): 51-62.
- European Commission. 2009. Regulation (EC) no 443/2009 of the European parliament and of the council setting emission performance standards for new passenger cars as part of the community's integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles.
- European Commission. 2015. State of the art on Alternative Fuels Transport Systems in the European Union.
- Eurostat. 2017. Share of energy from renewable sources — code: nrg_ind_335a http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=nrg_ind_335a&lang=en
- EESC. 2014. A Policy Framework for Climate and Energy in the Period from 2020 to 2030, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Brussels
- European Union. 2014. Directive 2014/94/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure Text with EEA relevance, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014L0094>

- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. 2014. Energy Efficiency and its Contribution to Energy Security and the 2030 Framework for Climate and Energy Policy. Brussels.
- DG-CLIMA. 2016. Road transport: reducing CO₂ emissions from vehicles - European commission. http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/vehicles/index_en.htm
- Faria I.G.D., and M.M. Andersen. 2017. Sectoral patterns versus firm-level heterogeneity-the dynamics of eco-innovation strategies in the automotive sector. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.*, 117: 266-281.
- Hafez O., and K. Bhattacharya. 2017. Optimal design of electric vehicle charging stations considering various energy resources. *Renew. Energy*, 107: 576-589
- Hackbarth A., and R. Madlener. 2013. Consumer preferences for alternative fuel vehicles: a discrete choice analysis. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 25: 5-17.
- Hidrué M., Parsons G., Kempton W., and M. Gardner. 2011. Willingness to pay for electric vehicles and their attributes, *Resour. Energy Econ.* 33 (3): 686-705.
- Hoën A., and M.J. Koetse. 2014. A choice experiment on alternative fuel vehicle preferences of private car owners in the Netherlands. *Transp. Res. A* 61: 199-215.
- Hong J., Koo Y., Jeong G., and J. Lee. 2012. Ex-ante evaluation of profitability and government's subsidy policy on vehicle-to-grid system. *Energ. Policy* 42: 95-104.
- International Energy Agency (IEA). 2016. CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion: Highlights, OECD/IEA 2016
- Junquera B., Moreno B., and R. Alvarez. 2016. Analyzing consumer attitudes towards electric vehicle purchasing intentions in Spain: technological limitations and vehicle confidence, *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 109: 6-14.
- Krause R.M., Carley S.R., Lane B.W., and J.D. Graham. 2013. Perception and reality: public knowledge of plug-in electric vehicles in 21 U.S. cities, *Energy Policy* 63: 433-440.
- Krupa J.S., Rizzo D.M., Eppstein M.J., Lanute D.B., Gaalema D.E., Lakkaraju K., and C.E. Warrender. 2014. Analysis of a consumer survey on plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, *Transp. Res. Part A Policy Pract.* 64: 14-31.
- Larson P.L., Viafara J., Parsons R.V., and A. Elias. 2014. Consumer attitudes about electric cars: pricing analysis and policy implications, *Transp. Res. Part A Policy Pract.* 69: 299-314.
- Marotta A., and M. Tutuianu. 2012. Europe-centric light duty test cycle and differences with respect to the WLTP cycle Technical report - Task 7. Joint Research Centre.
- Morton C., Anable J., and J.D. Nelson. 2011. Assessing the importance of car meanings and attitudes in consumer evaluations of electric vehicles, *Energy Effic.* 9 (2): 495-509
- Nanaki E.A., and C.J. Koroneos. 2016. Climate change mitigation and deployment of electric vehicles in urban areas, *Renew. Energy*, 99: 1153-1160.
- Pastorello C., and G. Mellios. 2015. European environment agency, European topic centre for air pollution and climate change mitigation. Monitoring CO₂ emissions from passenger cars and vans in 2014. Luxembourg: Publications Office
- Qian, L., and D. Soopramanien. 2011. Heterogeneous consumer preferences for alternative fuel cars in China. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 16 (8): 607-613.
- Raczkowski, K., Schneider, F., and F. Laroche. 2017. The Impact of Regulation of the Road Transport Sector on Entrepreneurship and Economic Growth in the European Union, Motor Transport Institute.
- Rogers E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations* (5th Edition). Free Press.
- Tran M., Branister D., Bishop J.D.K., and M.D. MuCulloch. 2013. Simulating early adoption of alternative fuel vehicles for sustainability. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 80 (5): 865-875.
- Wolinetz M., and J. Axsen. 2017. How policy can build the plug-in electric vehicle market: insights from the respondent-based preference and constraints (REPAC) model. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 117: 238-250